

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1895	Leo Aryeh Mayer	1917	1917	1950		Israeli scholar of Islamic art and rector of the Hebrew University of Jerusalem	1895-1959
1895	Axel von Harnack	1920	1920	1960		German librarian, historian and philologist	1895-1974
1895	Alexandru Rosetti	1920	1924	1965		Romanian linguist, editor and memoirist	1895-1990
1895	Wolfgang Krause	1920	1920	1963		German linguist	1895-1970
1895	Alfredo Schiaffini	1921	1923	1971		Italian philologist and linguist	1895-1971
1895	Mikhail Bakhtin	1921	1949	1961		Russian philosopher, literary critic and scholar who worked on literary theory, ethics, and the philosophy of language	1895-1975
1895	Grigore Nandriș	1922	1922	1968		Romanian linguist, philologist and memorialist	1895-1968
1895	George R. Stewart	1922	1922	1980		American historian, toponymist, novelist, and a professor of English	1895-1980
1895	Philippe Stern	1922	1927	1965		French art historian	1895-1979
1895	Ruth Sawtell Wallis	1922	1929	1974 w		American academic and physical anthropologist	1895-1978
1895	Helen Adolf	1923	1923	1979 w		Austrian-American linguist and literature scholar	1895-1998
1895	Melville J. Herskovits	1923	1923	1963		American anthropologist who helped establish African and African-American studies in American academia	1895-1963
1895	Jerzy Kuryłowicz	1924	1927	1965		Polish linguist (Indo-European languages)	1895-1978
1895	Valentin Voloshinov	1924	No	1936		Russian linguist (literary theory and Marxist theory of ideology)	1895-1936
1895	Paul Dottin	1924		1957		French French linguist and university professor	1895-1967
1895	James Germain Février	1924	1931	1972		French historian and philologist	1895-1976
1895	Raymond Lebègue	1925		1965		French literary historian	1895-1984
1895	A. S. P. Woodhouse	1927	No	1957		Canadian professor of English	1895-1964
1895	J. D. Unwin	1927		1936		British English ethnologist and social anthropologist	1895-1936
1895	Will Erich Peuckert	1927	1927	1959		German folklorist	1895-1969
1895	Iris Barry	1928		1951 w		British-American film critic and curator of the film department of the New York Museum of Modern Art	1895-1969
1895	Ingerid Dal	1930	1930	1965 w		Norwegian linguist (German, English and the Nordic languages)	1895-1985
1895	Kita Chkhenkeli	1938	1938	1963		Georgian linguist	1895-1963
1895	Charles Leslie Wrenn	1939	1939	1963		British the Rawlinson and Bosworth Professor of Anglo-Saxon	1895-1969

1895	Eslanda Goode Robeson	1946	1946	1958 w	American anthropologist, author, actor and civil rights activist	1895-1965
1895	Carobeth Laird	1964		1984 w	American ethnografer and linguist	1895-1983
1896	Helen C. White	1917	1924	1965 w	American professor of English	1896-1967
1896	Stella Kramrisch	1919	1919	1979 w	American pioneering art historian and curator who was the leading specialist on Indian art for most of the 20th century	1896-1993
1896	Hans Heinrich Schaeder	1920	1920	1957	German orientalist and Iranologist	1896-1957
1896	Erna Gunther	1920	1921	1969 w	American anthropologist	1896-1982
1896	Byron Khun de Prorok	1920	No	1954	Hungarian-American amateur archaeologist, anthropologist, and author of four travelogues	1896-1954
1896	Karl August Wittfogel	1920		1966	German-American playwright, historian, and sinologist	1896-1988
1896	Georges Dossin	1921	1921	1966	Belgian archaeologist, Assyriologist and art historian	1896-1983
1896	Kurt F. Reinhardt	1921		1962	German-American Germanist, philosopher and educator who was Professor at the Department of Modern European Languages and of the German Studies	1896-1983
1896	Amado Alonso	1922	1927	1952	Spanish-Argentinean philologist, linguist and literary critic	1896-1952
1896	Bruno Snell	1922	1922	1959	German classical philologist	1896-1986
1896	Bruno Migliorini	1922	1922	1975	Italian linguist and philologist, esperantist, author of one of the first scientific histories of Italian language	1896-1975
1896	Mihai Ralea	1922	1922	1964	Romanian social scientist, cultural journalist, and political figure	1896-1964
1896	Gustav Ecke	1922	1922	1971	German-American historian of art (China)	1896-1971
1896	Esther Schiff Goldfrank	1923		1957 w	American anthropologist	1896-1997
1896	Carsten Høeg	1925	1925	1961	Danish professor of classical philology and a Juris Doctor at the University of Copenhagen	1896-1961
1896	Mehmet Aga-Oglu	1926	1926	1949	Turkish Islamic art historian	1896-1949
1896	Anne Holtsmark	1927	1927	1960 w	Norwegian philologist	1896-1974
1896	Sophie Bledsoe Aberle	1927	1927	1970 w	American anthropologist, physician and nutritionist known for her work with Pueblo people	1896-1996
1896	Boris Unbegaun	1928	1935	1965	Russian-German linguist and philologist, expert in Slavic studies (Slavic languages and literature)	1896-1973

1896	Sirarpie Der Nersessian	1929	1936	1978 w	Armenian art historian, who specialized in Armenian and Byzantine studies	1896-1989
1896	Roman Jakobson	1930	1930	1970	Russian-Czech Linguist and literary theorist	1896-1982
1896	Oskar Mosfjeld	1949	1950	1963	Norwegian literary scholar	1896-1977
1897	Robert Redfield	1918	1928	1958	American anthropologist and ethnolinguist, whose ethnographic work in Tepoztlán, Mexico is considered a landmark of Latin American ethnography	1897-1958
1897	Károly Kerényi	1919	1919	1966	Hungarian scholar in classical philology and one of the founders of modern studies of Greek mythology	1897-1973
1897	Lucien Tesnière	1920	1920	1947	French prominent and influential linguist	1897-1954
1897	I. L. G. Sutherland	1920	1920	1952	New Zealand notable New Zealand ethnologist and university professor	1897-1952
1897	H. D. F. Kitto	1920	1920	1962	British classical scholar of Cornish ancestry	1897-1982
1897	Kenneth Emory	1921	1946	1983	American anthropologist who played a key role in shaping modern anthropology in Oceania	1897-1992
1897	Ainsworth O'Brien-Moore	1922	1922	1936	American classical philologist	1897-1936
1897	Albrecht Goetze	1922	1922	1965	German-American Hittitologist.	1897-1971
1897	Frederic Spiegelberg	1922	1922	1962	German-American Stanford University professor of Asian religions	1897-1994
1897	Giacomo Devoto	1923		1963	Italian linguist	1897-1974
1897	Hamit Zübeyir Koşay	1923	1923	1969	Turkish archaeologist, ethnographer, writer and folklore researcher	1897-1984
1897	Nicholas Poppe	1924	No	1968	Russian linguist (Mongolic languages)	1897-1991
1897	Stephen J. Herben Jr.	1924	1924	1962	American philologist	1897-1967
1897	Aurélien Sauvageot	1924	1930	1967	French linguist (Finno-Ugric languages)	1897-1988
1897	Ernst Waldschmidt	1924		1965	German orientalist and Indologist	1897-1985
1897	George Murdock	1925	1925	1973	American anthropologist (empirical approach to ethnological studies and of family and kinship structures across differing cultures)	1897-1985
1897	O. H. E. Burmester	1925		1967	British specialist in Arabic Coptology	1897-1977
1897	Frank H. H. Roberts	1926	1926	1966	American archaeologist and anthropologist, who was the final director of the Bureau of American Ethnology of the Smithsonian Institution	1897-1966
1897	Richard Beck	1926	1926	1967	Icelandic-American literary historian, author and poet	1897-1980

1897	Marcel Raymond	1927	1927	1962	Swiss literary critic who specialized in French literature	1897-1981	
1897	Bernhard Kummer	1927	1927	1945	German (Nazi) Germanist who was appointed to a professorship in the Nazi era and whose writings have been influential among postwar neo-Nazis	1897-1962	
1897	Benjamin Lee Whorf	1928	No	1941	American linguist and fire prevention engineer	1897-1941	
1897	Zenta Mauriņa	1928	1938	1963	w	Latvian writer, essayist and researcher in philology	1897-1978
1897	Joseph G. Fucilla	1928	1928	1966	American Hispanist and lexicographer	1897-1981	
1897	Samuel Noah Kramer	1929	1929	1968	Ukrainian-American one of the world's leading Assyriologists and a world-renowned expert in Sumerian history and Sumerian language	1897-1990	
1897	Octave Merlier	1930		1961	French expert on the Modern Greek language	1897-1976	
1897	Jean Boutière	1930	1930	1967	French philologist, specialist in Romance philology	1898-1967	
1897	Jocelyn Toynbee	1934	1934	1962	w	British English archaeologist and art historian	1897-1985
1897	Martiros Aslanov	1938		1967	Russian founder of the Moscow school of Pashto studies in Russia	1897-1977	
1897	Theodora Kroeber	1959	No	1978	w	American writer and anthropologist, best known for her accounts of several Native Californian cultures	1897-1979
1898	Eiliv Skard	1922	1931	1962	Norwegian classical philologist	1898-1978	
1898	Gerhard Storz	1922	1922	1964	German scholar, an educationalist, a politician and an author-journalist (" language therapist ")	1898-1983	
1898	Enrico Cerulli	1922	1898	1940	Italian scholar of Somali and Ethiopian studies, a governor and a diplomat	1898-1988	
1898	Nikolai Dmitriev	1922	1922	1954	Russian professor, an outstanding Orientalist-Turkologist	1898-1954	
1898	Helene Homeyer	1922	1922	1963	w	German Classical philologist, linguist and Central Latin philologist	1898-1996
1898	Joachim Wach	1922	1922	1955	German religious scholar, who emphasised a distinction between the history of religion (Religionswissenschaft) and the philosophy of religion	1898-1955	
1898	Gustav Haloun	1923	1923	1951	Czech sinologist	1898-1951	
1898	István Kniezsa	1924		1965	Hungarian linguist and Slavist	1898-1965	
1898	Georges Dumézil	1924	1924	1968	French comparative philologist best known for his analysis of sovereignty and power in Proto-Indo-European religion and society	1898-1986	

1898 August Closs	1924		1964	Austrian-British professor of German studies	1898-1990
1898 Hans Krahe	1925		1965	German philologist and linguist (Illyrian languages)	1898-1965
1898 Sara Haardt	1925		1935 w	American author and professor of English literature	1898-1935
1898 Leiv Amundsen	1926	1933	1968	Norwegian librarian and philologist	1898-1987
1898 Johannes Rahder	1926	1926	1965	Dutch Orientalist, professor of Japanese	1898-1988
1898 Ruth Bunzel	1926	1928	1966 w	American anthropologist, known for her studies of the Zuni people and of alcoholism in two Latin American villages	1898-1990
1898 Dámaso Alonso	1928	1928	1982	Spanish poet, philologist and literary critic	1898-1990
1898 Maurice Bowra	1928		1970	British English classical scholar, literary critic and academic, known for his wit	1898-1971
1898 Mariella Gable	1929	1934	1958 w	American academic, writer, and literary critic	1898-1985
1898 Paul Sidney Martin	1929	1929	1972	American anthropologist and archaeologist	1898-1974
1898 Marcel Griaule	1930	1938	1956	French author and anthropologist known for his studies of the Dogon people of West Africa, and for pioneering ethnographic field studies in France	1898-1956
1898 Kenneth Willis Clark	1931		1961	Greek palaeographer; area of interest: Greek New Testament manuscripts, and author of numerous books	1898-1979
1898 Roger Bastide	1931		1968	French sociologist and anthropologist, specialist in sociology and Brazilian literature	1898-1974
1898 Aziz Suryal Atiya	1931	1933	1959	Egyptian Coptologist who was a Coptic historian and scholar and an expert in Islamic and Crusades studies	1898-1988
1898 Suzanne Comhaire-Sylvain	1937		1975 w	Haitian anthropologist (first woman)	1898-1975
1898 W. Lloyd Warner	1937		1970	American pioneering anthropologist and sociologist noted for applying the techniques of British functionalism to understanding American culture	1898-1970
1898 Reginald Horace Blyth	1942	1954	1964	British English author and devotee of Japanese culture (Zen and on haiku poetry)	1898-1964
1898 Louis Eugene King	1968	1966	1968	Afro-American anthropologist	1898-1981
1899 Erik Holtved	1914	1944	1968	Danish artist, archaeologist, linguist, and ethnologist	1899-1981
1899 Lauri Hakulinen	1916	No	1962	Finnish professor of Finnish and the director of the Finnish Dictionary Fund	1899-1985
1899 Max Eiselen	1920	1924	1960	South African anthropologist and linguist	1899-1977

1899	Arno Schirokauer	1921	1921	1954	German-Jewish literary scholar	1899-1954
1899	Adolf Ellegard Jensen	1922	1922	1964	German one of the most important German ethnologists of the first half of the 20th century	1899-1965
1899	Johann Leo Weisgerber	1923	1923	1967	German (Lorraine-born) linguist who also specialized in Celtic linguistics	1899-1985
1899	Adolf Leschnitzer	1923	1923	1966	American writer-researcher, historian and teacher, specialising in Jewish and German studies	1899-1980
1899	Louis Hjelmslev	1924	1932	1965	Danish linguist (the Copenhagen School of linguistics)	1899-1965
1899	Jón Helgason	1924		1972	Icelandic philologist and poet	1899-1986
1899	Hans Herter	1924	1924	1967	German Classical philologist, Director of the Rheinischen Museum für Philologie	1899-1984
1899	Mildred Trotter	1924	1924	1967 w	American pioneer as a forensic historian and forensic anthropologist	1899-1991
1899	Lūcija Jēruma-Krastiņa	1924	1938	1948 w	Latvian anatomist and anthropologist, and one of the first women to be awarded a doctorate from a Latvian university	1899-1968
1899	Eugène Vinaver	1925	1925	1966	French-British literary scholar	1899-1979
1899	Paul Leser	1925	1925	1968	German Jewish-American ethnologist	1899-1984
1899	George Călinescu	1925	1936	1965	Romanian literary critic, historian, novelist, academician and journalist, and a writer of classicist and humanist tendencies	1899-1965
1899	Pierre Chantraine	1926	No	1969	French linguist	1899-1974
1899	John A. Wilson	1926	1926	1968	American Egyptologist, the Andrew MacLeish Distinguished Service Professor at the University of Chicago	1899-1976
1899	Charles Perrat	1926		1970	French paleographer, professor	1899-1976
1899	Gösta Montell	1926	No	1966	Swedish ethnographer	1899-1975
1899	Voldemar Vaga	1926	1964	1969	Estonian art and architecture historian and teacher	1899-1999
1899	Frederic Ewen	1927	1932	1952	American professor of English literature	1899-1988
1899	Harold Walter Bailey	1927		1967	British eminent English scholar of Khotanese, Sanskrit, and the comparative study of Iranian languages	1899-1996

1899 Gladys Tantaquidgeon	1928 No		1998 w	American Mohegan medicine woman , anthropologist, author, tribal council member	1899-2005
1899 Борис Граков	1929	1939	1970	Russian archaeologist (Scythian and Sarmatian archeology, classical philology and ancient epigraphy)	1899-1970
1899 Emil Petrovici	1930	1930	1968	Romanian linguist, dialectologist and Slavist	1899-1968
1899 Harold Walter Bailey	1930		1967	British eminent English scholar of Khotanese, Sanskrit, and the comparative study of Iranian languages	1899-1996
1899 Audrey Richards	1931	1931	1967 w	British social anthropologist, pioneer in sub-Saharan Africa	1899-1984
1899 Viola Garfield	1931	1933	1970 w	American anthropologist best known for her work on the social organization and plastic arts of the Tsimshian nation in British Columbia and Alaska	1899-1983
1899 Bertil Lundman	1931	1945	1970	Swedish anthropologist	1899-1993
1899 Wilhelm Wissmann	1932	1932	1959	German Comparative linguist	1899-1966
1899 Lasgush Poradeci	1933	1933	1974	Albanian philologist, poet, translator, writer and pioneer of modern Albanian literature	1899-1987
1899 María del Rosario Gutiérrez Eskildsen	1934		1979 w	Mexican lexicographer, linguist, educator, and poet	1899-1979
1899 Rosario María Gutiérrez Eskildsen	1934	1944	1953 w	Mexican lexicographer, linguist, educator, and poet	1899-1979
1899 Lydia Cabrera	1936		1960 w	Cuban independent ethnographer	1899-1991
1899 Tha Myat	1948 No		1954	Burmese (Myanmarian) linguist	1899-1977
1899 Ivar Skarland	1948	1948	1965	Norwegian anthropologist	1899-1965